

THE ROLE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING IN FORMING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE ECONOMISTS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7699408>

ELSEVIER

Kurbanova Niginabonu Pardayevna

Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract: The article is devoted to the role of foreign languages in forming professional competences of students learning economics at universities. The article proves that foreign languages are extremely important for a future career of a young specialist in today's highly competitive and oversaturated labor market. Higher education is aimed to develop general and professional competences, while learning a foreign language is targeted at developing vital analytical and communicative skills, which contribute to students' ability not only to apply foreign language in daily and business life, but also to develop themselves further

Keywords: professional competence, foreign language, student, knowledge, skills..

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 03-03-2023

Accepted: 04-03-2023

Published: 22-03-2023

РОЛЬ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ ЭКОНОМИСТОВ

Курбанова Нигинабону Пардаевна

Ташкентский Государственный Экономический Университет

Abstract: Статья посвящена роли иностранных языков в формировании профессиональных компетенций студентов, изучающих экономику в вузах. В статье доказывается, что иностранные языки чрезвычайно важны для будущей карьеры молодого специалиста на современном высококонкурентном и перенасыщенном рынке труда. Высшее образование направлено на развитие общих и профессиональных компетенций, в то время как изучение иностранного языка направлено на развитие жизненно важных аналитических и коммуникативных навыков, которые способствуют способности студентов не только применять иностранный язык в повседневной и деловой жизни, но и развиваться дальше

Keywords: профессиональная компетентность, иностранный язык, студент, знания, навыки.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 03-03-2023

Accepted: 04-03-2023

Published: 22-03-2023

Today in conditions of openness of the Uzbek market, widening of cultural and business links with foreign countries, high competitive labor market and increasing globalization, the role of foreign language learning is growing significantly. Knowledge of foreign languages has already become a distinctive feature of well-educated people and skilled specialists as well as the main source of self-development and promotion.

Employers expect a lot from a young specialist, including the knowledge of foreign languages, at least English. Students also see the necessity of foreign language learning during their studies. For example, while preparing for course papers or looking for references while writing diploma works, students often refer to books and articles published in English, which can give them deeper information of the subject they research. Young specialists who have an advanced level of a foreign language can expect from the future employer a higher salary, bonuses and business assignments abroad. They do realize that most of the big companies operating in Russia focus on penetrating the foreign markets: these companies accept international standards of conducting business and financial reporting, communicate with foreign partners and enter new markets. At the same time, more and more students are dreaming about working for big multinational companies, which also seems impossible without strong language skills.

Studying a foreign language assumes that a student learns four main aspects of the language: speaking, reading, grammar and listening. However, at university students acquire skills not only mentioned above, but also the ones which will allow them to use their knowledge in business sphere. At economic educational programs students learn vocabulary and language clichés connected with different topics of business, e.g. marketing, selling, finance etc. At the same time, educational programs for the Bachelor and Master degrees in foreign languages are gaining popularity among the students. Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, High School of Economics, MGIMO and other universities are offering such programs.

Using professional-competence approach for defining skills and knowledge, Ronald Epstein and Edward Hundert determine professional competence as the habitual and judicious use of communication, knowledge, technical skills, reasoning, emotions, values, and reflection in daily practice for the benefit of the individual and community being served [Epstein, Hundert, 2002]. We see professional competence as the main part of higher education and as the main characteristic of a person. The main advantage of professional-competence approach is that it focuses not on theoretical aspects, but on practical skills, qualities, experience and knowledge of a specialist. Competence does not imply that theory is useless, it means synergy of theory and practice and even more. The main distinguishing feature of competence from theory is that professional competence allows students and young specialist to acquire new skills and knowledge on their own after they graduate.

The Issue of the Ministry of Education of the Uzbekistan «About federal state educational standards of higher education for economists» states that a student acquires general cultural, general professional and professional competences.

The following main general cultural and general professional competences are acquired by a student during the study process:

- The ability to communicate orally and in written form in Uzbek and foreign languages to solve tasks of interpersonal and intercultural communication;
- The ability to solve standard tasks of professional activity on the basis of informational and bibliographic culture using informational technologies;
- The ability for self-management and self-education;
- The ability to use foreign references in conducting analyses and research;
- The ability to collect, analyze and process data to solve professional tasks.

Most of these competences do not imply strong skills in foreign languages, which, however, can be developed by learning. Students of senior courses in Tashkent State University of Economics are particularly interested in business dilemma studying which is aimed at reinforcing language knowledge in simulating real business situations during the tutorials. The importance of business dilemma solving connotes the students' involvement in finding a well-grounded solution to the earlier unfamiliar business problem. The students' attention gets concentrated on contradictions and doubts which are extremely motivating for realizing cognitive and creative activities in each student and apply the received knowledge in practice. [Bernatskaya, Muratova, 2015]

Modern ways of learning foreign languages focus mostly on speaking skills. Consequently, during language classes students are solving different cases connected with real business life in teams. While working with these tasks, they communicate much with each other, discuss different ways of solving problems and use brainstorming methods. Students go into the real situation and such kind of interactive tasks allow them to improve their verbal thinking and interactive skills.

Students acquire communicative competence during foreign language tutorials at university. Communicative competence includes five other competences which allow young specialist to apply their language skills fully. These competences are:

1 Linguistic (or language) competence which allows people to understand other people's thoughts and express their own opinion orally and in written form;

2 Speech competence (also called socio-linguistic) means that a person knows the ways of expressing thoughts using this language and can use it in their own speech;

3 Socio-cultural competence implies that a person knows national and cultural features of native-speakers: their traditions, customs, social stereotypes, history, culture etc.;

4 Social competence is reflected by person's ability and desire to speak with other people using this language;

5 Strategic competence allows a person to fill the gaps basing on their knowledge and experience.

Acquiring these competences allows students to use foreign language not only in their daily life, but also successfully apply it in business practice, negotiating with partners, speaking at conferences and presentations or analyzing foreign references. Key competences (i.e. language competence) ought to be formed as a result of language learning as a part of the Academic Curriculum in the university. The students are supposed to master the basics of the language for communication.

Successfulness of competence approach can be measured by student's ability to cope with high competitiveness on labor market.

As a result, learning foreign language in higher educational institutions involves not only learning language as a discipline, but also acquiring skills, knowledge and experience which will be useful in practice. Practical tasks conducted at seminars allow students to get acquainted with real situations which they will face in working environment and enables them to get ready to overcome potential future difficulties at work. Improvement of foreign language skills contributes much to overall knowledge and forms vital professional competences. Communicative professional competence is a great advantage of every student who is looking for a job in economic sphere. Labor market of economists is oversaturated with yesterday's students and communicative competence makes an applicant unique and more desirable by an employer. In turn, professional competence is what makes a young specialist a real professional in his sphere.

REFERENCES:

Акопян Л.Г. Компетентностный подход в иноязычной подготовке студентов неязыковых вузов // Интеллект, Оренбург, ОГУ. – 2011 - №1.

Симаева Н.П. Профессиональные компетенции студентов экономических и юридических специальностей. // Вестник ВолГУ. – 2010 - №12 (6).

Бернацкая М.В., Муратова О.А. Плюсы и минусы использования интерактивных технологий при обучении иностранному языку студентов неязыковых вузов // Концепт. – 2015 - № 05 (май).

Mulder, M. Conceptions of Professional Competence. // International Handbook of Research. Professional and Practice-based Learning. – 2014 с. 107-137.

Ronald M. Epstein, Edward M. Hundert. Defining and Assessing Professional Competence. - JAMA. – 2002 - №2.